

Superoxide catalyzed oxidation of 4-alkylsubstituted pyrazol-5-ones to 4-alkyl-4-hydroxy substituted pyrazol-5-ones

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Abstract : Superoxide ion, generated *in situ* by the phase transfer reaction of potassium superoxide and tetraethylammonium bromide, brings about an easy oxidation of different 4-alkylsubstituted pyrazol-5-ones to yield 4-alkyl-4-hydroxy pyrazol-5-ones in reasonably good yields.

Keywords : Superoxide catalysis, substituted pyrazole, oxidation.

Superoxide ion has come to the forefront of current research owing to its demonstrated biochemical implications and as a species of relatively unexplored chemical reactivity¹. The ability of superoxide ion to function as a multipotent reagent has made the chemistry of this radical anion quite enigmatic². However, the role and versatility of this novel reagent for organic synthetic purposes is still limited.

As a part of our research interest to extend the application of superoxide ion in organic synthesis³, we wish to demonstrate the use of *in situ* generated tetraethylammonium superoxide (Et₄NO₂) for accomplishing a facile and efficient oxidation of a number of 4-substituted pyrazolones to 4-substituted 4-hydroxypyrazolones (Scheme 1).

R₁ = C₆H₅, CH₃; R₂ = CH₃; R₃ = CH₃, C₂H₅, n-C₃H₇, n-C₄H₉, C₆H₁₃, C₆H₅CH₂

Scheme 1

The substrates, 3,4-dimethyl-1-phenylpyrazol-5-one (**1a**), 4-ethyl-3-methyl-1-phenylpyrazol-5-one (**1b**), 4-propyl-3-methyl-1-phenylpyrazol-5-one (**1c**), 4-butyl-3-methyl-1-phenylpyrazol-5-one (**1d**), 4-hexyl-3-methyl-1-phenylpyrazol-5-one (**1e**), 4-benzyl-3-methyl-1-phenylpyrazol-5-one (**1f**), 1-phenyl-3,4-cyclohexanopyrazol-5-one (**1g**) and 4-benzyl-1,3-dimethylpyrazol-5-one (**1h**) were made to react with KO₂ and

Et₄NBr in dry DMF at room temperature. As an outcome, the substrates **1a-h** are readily oxidised to their corresponding 4-hydroxyl derivatives **2a-h** in reasonably good yields under the mild reactions conditions of Et₄NO₂. The results of the investigation are summarised in Table 1.

The reactions were accomplished by using 2.0-fold molar excess of KO₂ and 1.0-fold molar of Et₄NBr over the substrate **1a-h** in anhydrous DMF. Generally, the reactions were carried out for 2–4 h at room temperature. The total disappearance of the starting material was checked by TLC, then the reaction mixture was quenched with cold brine solution and worked up to afford the products in excellent yields. All the products are known compounds and have been identified by the comparison of their physical and spectral data with those of the authentic samples.

Experimental

Potassium superoxide and tetraethylammonium bromide were procured from Aldrich, USA and were used as received. The substrates **1a-h** were prepared according to the literature procedures⁴. The other reagents and solvents were of A.R. grade and were used after necessary purification. ¹H NMR spectra were obtained in CDCl₃ at 300 MHz. Chemical shift are given with respect to TMS as the internal standard.

*Reaction of in situ generated superoxide ion with 4-alkylsubstituted pyrazol-5-ones*¹: *General procedure* : Potassium superoxide (0.68 g; 0.0096 mol) and tetraethylammonium bromide¹ (1.01 g; 0.0048 mol) were weighed under nitrogen atmosphere using atmosbag and were transferred into a three-necked round bottom flask containing

Table 1. Oxidation of 4-alkylsubstituted pyrazol-5-ones to 4-alkyl-4-hydroxy pyrazol-5-ones mediated by Et₄NO₂

Sl. no.	Substrate	Product	Yield (%)	M.p. (°C) Obs. (Lit.) ⁵
1.	 2a	82	103–104 °C (105 °C)	
2.	 2b	86	129 °C (130 °C)	
3.	 2c	81	114–116 °C (116 °C)	
4.	 2d	77	92–94 °C (95 °C)	
5.	 2e	72	111 °C (110 °C)	
6.	 2f	88	144–145 °C (145 °C)	
7.	 2g	66	145 °C (145 °C)	
8.	 2h	81	155 °C (156 °C)	

dry DMF (20 ml) and fitted with a dropping funnel, an inlet nitrogen bubbler, a magnetic stirrer and a Liebig condenser guarded with drying tube. The reaction mixture was stirred for 15 min and to it was then added 4-substituted pyrazolone

1 (0.0048 mol). Nitrogen was bubbled continuously while stirring for 2–4 h at room temperature. The completion of the reaction was checked by TLC. The mixture was treated with brine solution and extracted with diethyl ether (20 × 3). The

Note

combined ether extract was dried over Na₂SO₄ (anhyd.), filtered, evaporated and recrystallized from water or aqueous ethanol to furnish the pure product **2**.

- (2a) ¹H NMR (CDCl₃), δ = 0.8 (3H, s, CH₃); 1.4 (3H, s, CH₃); 2.0 (1H, s, OH); 7.00–7.24 (3H, q, ArH); 7.63 (2H, d, ArH).
- (2b) ¹H NMR (CDCl₃), δ = 0.9 (3H, s, CH₃); 0.94 (3H, t, CH₃); 1.9 (2H, q, CH₂); 2.0 (1H, s, OH); 7.00–7.24 (3H, q, ArH); 7.63 (2H, d, ArH).
- (2c) ¹H NMR (CDCl₃), δ = 0.8 (3H, s, CH₃); 0.90 (3H, t, CH₃); 1.3 (2H, m, CH₂); 1.8 (2H, q, CH₂); 2.0 (1H, s, OH); 7.00–7.24 (3H, q, ArH); 7.63 (2H, d, ArH).
- (2d) ¹H NMR (CDCl₃), δ = 0.9 (3H, s, CH₃); 0.95 (3H, t, CH₃); 1.29–1.33 (4H, m, CH₂-CH₂); 1.7 (2H, t, CH₂); 2.0 (1H, s, OH); 7.00–7.24 (3H, q, ArH); 7.63 (2H, d, ArH).
- (2e) ¹H NMR (CDCl₃), δ = 0.9 (3H, s, CH₃); 0.95 (3H, t, CH₃); 1.29–1.34 (8H, m, CH₂-CH₂-CH₂-CH₂); 1.8 (2H, t, CH₂); 2.0 (1H, s, OH); 7.00–7.24 (3H, q, ArH); 7.63 (2H, d, ArH).
- (2f) ¹H NMR (CDCl₃), δ = 0.8 (3H, s, CH₃); 3.1 (2H, s, CH₂-Ar); 2.0 (1H, s, OH); 7.00–7.24 (3H, q, ArH of two phenyl ring); 7.12 (2H, d, ArH); 7.63 (2H, d, ArH).
- (2g) ¹H NMR (CDCl₃), δ = 1.26–1.29 (4H, m, cyclohexane); 1.30–1.80 (4H, t, cyclohexane); 2.0 (1H, s, OH); 7.00–7.24 (3H, q, ArH); 7.62 (2H, d, ArH).
- (2h) ¹H NMR (CDCl₃), δ = 0.9 (3H, s, CH₃); 2.8 (2H, s, CH₂-Ar); 2.0 (1H, s, OH); 7.08 (1H, q, ArH); 7.12 (2H, d, ArH); 7.18 (2H, q, ArH).

Conclusion :

In conclusion, the present report demonstrates the application of *in situ* generated tetraethylammonium superoxide for a mild and efficient oxidation of 4-alkylsubstituted pyrazol-5-ones to 4-alkyl-4-hydroxypyrazol-5-ones, under non-aqueous conditions.

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